

OCEAN ICE News – April 2026

OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System.

OCEAN ICE News is a monthly newsletter updating about the project's progress, results, and other exciting events! Be sure to follow us on LinkedIn to stay informed.

Welcome!

Welcome to April's edition of OCEAN ICE News. We're excited to bring you the latest updates from the OCEAN ICE community.

In this issue, you'll meet our featured researcher of the month and catch up on key activities, such as OCEAN ICE at TIPMIP GA and the CMIP7 Community Workshop, and highlighting March's Climate Coffee. We have some upcoming Climate Coffee's that you can register for in April and June. Don't forget to mark your calendars for the upcoming events where OCEAN ICE will be represented.

We hope you enjoy exploring this month's updates, and we look forward to sharing more in May!

Meet the Team: David Bett

Check out our latest 'Meet the Team' feature on David Bett, an ice-ocean modeller working at the British Antarctic Survey.

Read the feature on David [here](#).

Stay tuned for more features from our Research Team in OCEAN ICE.

Catching up on the Latest OCEAN ICE Activities

OCEAN ICE at TIPMIP GA and the CMIP7 Community Workshop

OCEAN ICE presented work at the TIPMIP GA at the University in Tokyo and the CMIP7 Community Workshop in Kyoto. Work was presented from WP6 on the theme of modelling ice sheet freshwater fluxes in Earth System Models.

Robin Smith convened a side-session discussing the importance of including ice sheet processes and freshwater fluxes in climate simulations that was well attended,

Read the full article [here](#).

OCEAN ICE Climate coffee – March

Climate Coffee with Giulia Bonino on Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

Marine heatwaves, extended periods of elevated sea surface temperature, impact society and ecosystems, and a deeper understanding of their drivers is needed to predict and mitigate adverse effects. These events can be particularly severe in the Mediterranean Sea during the summer, although the factors controlling their occurrence and duration are not fully understood. Here, we use a comprehensive multi-decadal macroevent dataset and a cluster analysis to investigate the atmospheric dynamics preceding the largest summer marine heatwaves in the Mediterranean Sea. Our study identifies the favourable conditions leading up to marine heatwave peaks and reveals that their main synoptic cause in the Mediterranean Sea is the combined effect of persistent subtropical anticyclonic ridges and associated weakening of prevailing wind systems. When persistent subtropical ridges are established over the region, the resulting decrease in wind speeds reduces latent heat loss to the atmosphere, which accounts for over 70% of the total heat flux in affected regions. This reduction, combined with a moderate increase in short-wave radiation, generates and intensifies marine heatwaves. This synergistic relationship is a key mechanism for skilfully predicting such atmospheric circulation patterns and realistically simulating their impacts on the marine environment.

CLIMATE ACTION DAYS

EUROPEAN CLIMATE PACT

26 March 4 pm Climate Coffee

Mediterranean summer marine heatwaves triggered by weaker winds under subtropical ridges

Danish Meteorological Institute **ECRA** **Obs Sea Clim** **OCEAN:ICE** **Funded by the European Union**

Join us!

Climate Coffees

Since its relaunch, the [Climate Coffee series](#) has been in full swing. If you've missed any of the recent ones, don't you worry, you may catch up [here](#).

Climate Coffee

Upcoming Events

Climate Coffee

We have an upcoming Climate Coffee in April and June, make sure you register for all of them through the link on [OCEAN ICE](#).

Climate Coffee with Jens Terhaar on Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected

23 April 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CET)

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, which consists of three wavy lines in blue and yellow. To the right of the logo, the text reads: 'Climate Coffee', '23 April 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST', 'Online', 'Jens Terhaar (University Bern)', and 'Record sea surface temperature jump in 2023–2024 unlikely but not unexpected'. A circular portrait of Jens Terhaar is on the right side. At the bottom, there are logos for the Danish Meteorological Institute, ECRA, TipESM, Obs Sea Clim, OCEAN:ICE, and the European Union. Several coffee beans are scattered around the text.

Climate Coffee with Torsten Albrecht on Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming

18 June 2026, 10:00 – 10:45 (CEST)

The poster features the 'Climate Coffee' logo on the left, which consists of three wavy lines in blue and yellow. To the right of the logo, the text reads: 'Climate Coffee', 'Thu 18 June 2026 | 10:00 - 10:45 CEST', 'Online', 'Torsten Albrecht (Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research)', and 'Mapping tipping risks from Antarctic ice basins under global warming'. A circular portrait of Torsten Albrecht is on the right side. At the bottom, there are logos for the Danish Meteorological Institute, ECRA, TipESM, Obs Sea Clim, OCEAN:ICE, and the European Union. Several coffee beans are scattered around the text.

Happening Soon

OCEAN ICE will be at these upcoming events. Will you also be there? Let us know!

- 3rd - 8th May 2026, [EGU 2026](#), Vienna, Austria
- 8th -19th August 2026, [SCAR Open Science Conference & Meetings](#), Norway, Oslo
- 17th - 19th August 2026, [FRISP Meeting 2026](#), Sweden, Kristineberg

Do you know of any exciting events that OCEAN ICE should be a part of? Shoot us a mail at oceanice.eu@gmail.com.

Are you following us on Social Media?

Stay up to date with OCEAN ICE on our following channels:

www.ocean-ice.eu

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/euoceanice/>

https://twitter.com/OCEANICE_EU

<https://fediscience.org/@OceanIceEU>

<https://www.facebook.com/OCEANICEEU/>

[OCEAN ICE \(@oceaniceeu.bsky.social\) — Bluesky](#)

Who is OCEAN ICE?

OCEAN ICE stands for Ocean-Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica: Impacts on Climate and the Earth System. OCEAN ICE is a Horizon Europe project, funded by the European Commission and UKRI. OCEAN ICE focus on understanding how the Antarctic ice sheet and the surrounding Southern Ocean influence our global climate and reduce the level of uncertainty around how much the Antarctic ice sheet will melt in the coming centuries. OCEAN ICE considers the critical role of feedbacks between ocean circulation, ice sheet change and tipping points and the global climate. [Find out more](#)

OCEAN:ICE

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